

PRISMA 2020 Checklist for Systematic Review

Title: Enterprise Resource Planning Systems in the Era of Intelligent Computing: A Comprehensive Survey of AI Integration, Security Frameworks, and Emerging Paradigms (2020–2026)

PRISMA 2020 Main Checklist

Section/Topic	#	Checklist Item	Location
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a systematic review.	Page 1 (Title)
ABSTRACT			
Abstract	2	See the PRISMA 2020 for Abstracts checklist.	Page 1 (Abstract)
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of existing knowledge.	Section 1.1
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of the objective(s) or question(s) the review addresses.	Section 1.2
METHODS			
Eligibility criteria	5	Specify the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the review and how studies were grouped for the syntheses.	Section 1.3, Supplementary S2
Information sources	6	Specify all databases, registers, websites, organisations, reference lists and other sources searched or consulted to identify studies.	Section 1.3 Phase 1
Search strategy	7	Present the full search strategies for all databases, registers and websites, including any filters and limits used.	Section 1.3 Phase 1, Supplementary S1
Selection process	8	Specify the methods used to decide whether a study met the inclusion criteria of the review.	Section 1.3 Phase 2-3, Supplementary S2
Data collection process	9	Specify the methods used to collect data from reports, including how many reviewers collected data from each report.	Section 1.3 Phase 4, Supplementary S3
Data items	10a	List and define all outcomes for which data were sought.	Section 1.3 Phase 4, Supplementary S3
	10b	List and define all other variables for which data were sought.	Section 1.3 Phase 4, Supplementary S3
Study risk of bias assessment	11	Specify the methods used to assess risk of bias in the included studies.	Section 1.3 Phase 3
Effect measures	12	Specify for each outcome the effect measure(s) used in the synthesis or presentation of results.	Sections 3-9 (domain-specific)
Synthesis methods	13a	Describe the processes used to decide which studies were eligible for each synthesis.	Section 1.3 Phase 5
	13b	Describe any methods required to prepare the data for presentation or synthesis.	Section 1.3 Phase 5
	13c	Describe any methods used to tabulate or visually display results of individual studies and syntheses.	Sections 3-10, Tables I-III, Figures 1-5
	13d	Describe any methods used to synthesize results and provide a rationale for the choice(s).	Section 1.3 Phase 5
	13e	Describe any methods used to explore possible causes of heterogeneity among study results.	Section 10.2
	13f	Describe any sensitivity analyses conducted to assess robustness of the synthesized results.	Section 11 (Limitations)
Reporting bias assessment	14	Describe any methods used to assess risk of bias due to missing results in a synthesis.	Section 11 (Limitations)
Certainty assessment	15	Describe any methods used to assess certainty (or confidence) in the body of	Section 1.3 Phase 3

evidence for an outcome.

RESULTS

Study selection	16a	Describe the results of the search and selection process.	Section 1.3, Figure (PRISMA Flow Diagram)
	16b	Give numbers of studies screened, assessed for eligibility, and included in the review, with reasons for exclusions at each stage.	PRISMA Flow Diagram, Supplementary S2
Study characteristics	17	Cite each included study and present its characteristics.	References, Supplementary S2-S3
Risk of bias in studies	18	Present assessments of risk of bias for each included study.	Section 1.3 Phase 3, Supplementary S2
Results of individual studies	19	For all outcomes, present, for each study: summary statistics and effect estimate and confidence interval.	Sections 3-9, Tables I-III
Results of syntheses	20a	For each synthesis, briefly summarise the characteristics and risk of bias among contributing studies.	Sections 3-10
	20b	Present results of all statistical syntheses conducted.	Sections 3-10, Tables I-III
	20c	Present results of all investigations of possible causes of heterogeneity among study results.	Section 10.2
	20d	Present results of all sensitivity analyses conducted.	Section 11 (Limitations)
Reporting biases	21	Present assessments of risk of bias due to missing results for each synthesis assessed.	Section 11 (Limitations)
Certainty of evidence	22	Present assessments of certainty (or confidence) in the body of evidence for each outcome assessed.	Section 1.3 Phase 3, Sections 3-9

DISCUSSION

Discussion	23a	Provide a general interpretation of the results in the context of other evidence.	Section 11.1-11.2
	23b	Discuss any limitations of the evidence included in the review.	Section 11.4
	23c	Discuss any limitations of the review processes used.	Section 11.4
	23d	Discuss implications of the results for practice, policy, and future research.	Sections 11.2-11.3

OTHER INFORMATION

Registration and protocol	24a	Provide registration information for the review, including register name and registration number.	N/A (Not pre-registered)
	24b	Indicate where the review protocol can be accessed.	N/A
	24c	Describe and explain any amendments to information provided at registration or in the protocol.	N/A
Support	25	Describe sources of financial or non-financial support for the review.	Not applicable
Competing interests	26	Declare any competing interests of review authors.	None declared
Availability of data, code and other materials	27	Report which of the following are publicly available and where they can be found: template data collection forms; data extracted from included studies; data used for all analyses; analytic code; any other materials used in the review.	Data Availability Statement

Notes

1. This systematic review was conducted following PRISMA 2020 guidelines.
2. Single-author review: All screening, data extraction, and analysis performed by one researcher.
3. Search period: January 2020 to January 2026
4. Total studies included: 147 peer-reviewed publications
5. Databases searched: IEEE Xplore, ACM Digital Library, ScienceDirect, SpringerLink, Google Scholar